

Effect of azolla green manure on rice yield

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We have studied azolla as a green manure in farmers' fields at Antananarivo (1,260 m altitude), comparing incorporated azolla (10 t fresh weight/ha) with 30 kg and 60 kg N as urea/ha and with a split 5 t fresh weight azolla/ha + 30 kg N as urea/ha. Azolla and urea were incorporated 1 wk before transplanting. The 10 t fresh azolla/ha was the equivalent of 26 kg N/ha.

Grain and straw yields with azolla and with urea. Antananarivo, Madagascar.

Treatment	Grain yield		Straw yield	
	t/ha	Increase (%) over control	t/ha	Increase (%) over control
No fertilizer	5.8	—	18.6	—
10 t azolla	7.4	29	23.2	25
5 t azolla + 30 kg N as urea	6.7	16	19.0	2
30 kg N (urea)	6.1	6	20.2	9
60 kg N (urea)	7.8	36	24.5	32
LSD (0.05)	0.6		2.3	

The trial was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. The azolla was the indigenous *Azolla pinnata* var. *africana*, the rice variety Rojofotsy 1285.

Soil was a sandy loam mineral hydromorph with pH 5.2, 1.13% total P, 0.155% P Olsen, 3% organic matter,

1.7% C, 0.18 meq exchangeable K/100 g.

N and azolla increased both grain and straw yields (see table). Yield was highest with 60 kg N as urea/ha, followed by that with 10 t fresh weight azolla/ha. Azolla + urea was better than urea alone. □

Green manure to sustain productivity and save nitrogen for rice in a rice - wheat cropping system

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We studied the effects of 3 green manure crops—*Sesbania esculentus* (janter), *Vigna sinensis* (cowpea), and *Crotalaria juncea* (sunn hemp)—at 3 ages of incorporation (40-, 50-, and 60d-old crops), with 60, 90, and 120 kg N/ha on yield of rice grown after wheat.

Soil was sandy loam (Typic Ustochrept) with pH 8.1, 0.32% organic C, and 14 kg Olsen's P/ha. Green manure crops were incorporated 1 d before transplanting rice. All plots received 13 kg P/ha and 24 kg K/ha at transplanting.

Burying sesbania, cowpea, and sunn hemp resulted in significantly higher rice productivity (Table 1). All green manure crops saved 60 kg N/ha (Table 2). □

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Table 1. Grain yield of rice with green manure. Ludhiana, India, 1985-87.

Treatment		Grain yield (t/ha)			
		1985	1986	1987	Mean
Fallow		6.8	8.1	6.1	7.0
Sesbania	40 d	7.6	9.6	7.8	8.3
	50 d	7.8	9.7	7.9	8.5
	60 d	7.7	9.7	7.8	8.4
Cowpea	40 d	8.1	10.3	7.8	8.7
	50 d	7.9	9.6	7.9	8.4
	60 d	7.7	9.6	7.8	8.4
Sunn hemp	40 d	7.8	9.6	7.7	8.3
	50 d	8.0	9.7	7.7	8.5
	60 d	8.1	9.7	7.8	8.5
LSD (P = 0.05)		0.8	0.7	0.8	0.8

Table 2. Interaction between green manure crops, stages, and N levels on rice yields.^a Ludhiana, India, 1985-87.

Treatment		Grain yield (t/ha)			Mean
		60 kg N/ha	90 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha	
Fallow		5.8	7.2	8.0	7.0
Sesbania	40 d	8.1	8.4	8.5	8.3
	50 d	8.4	8.6	8.4	8.5
	60 d	8.4	8.6	8.3	8.4
Cowpea	40 d	8.6	8.8	8.7	8.7
	50 d	8.4	8.4	8.5	8.4
	60 d	8.4	8.4	8.2	8.4
Sunn hemp	40 d	8.2	8.3	8.4	8.3
	50 d	8.3	8.5	8.6	8.5
	60 d	8.4	8.5	8.7	8.5
Mean		8.1	8.4	8.4	

^aMean of 3 yr, 1985-87. LSD (P = 0.05) for green manure crops and stages × N levels = 0.81.